

D8.6 ASHVIN ASSET PORTFOLIO

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ABSTRACT

Exploitation activities are critical components of any H2020-funded project's success. The following document provides a comprehensive summary of ASHVIN's strategy, business model, targeted market, challenges, competitors, and information about the conducted with the partners to brainstorm the key exploitable results. It lays out the current market insights and specifies the various market domains ASHVIN toolkit could target by pursuing its exploitation.

strategy.

KEYWORDS

Digital Twin, Building Information Modelling, Communication, Exploitation, Business Model

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ACRONYMS & DEFINITIONS

AECO	Architecture Engineering Construction and Operation
AI	Artificial Intelligence
BIM	Building Information Modelling
DT	Digital Twin
ER	Exploitable Results
EU	European Union
IoT	Internet of Things
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
VC	Venture Capital
WP	Work package
GEN	Generative Design
DES	Simulation-based real-time Construction site and logistics planning tool
4DV-D	4D Visualizer for Construction site Design
4DV-C	4D Visualizer for Construction monitoring
SMT	Safety Management Tool
CMT	Configuration Management Tool
RISA	Risk-based Status Assessment Tool
MatchFEM	Multi-physics model Matching Tool
GISI	GIS Integrator for digital twin-based Asset management
EBD	Evidence Based Design
UPC	Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya · Barcelona Tech
R&D	Research and Development
KPI	Key Performance Indicator

ASHVIN PROJECT

ASHVIN aims at enabling the European construction industry to significantly improve its productivity, while reducing cost and ensuring absolutely safe work conditions, by providing a proposal for a European wide digital twin standard, an open-source digital twin platform integrating IoT and image technologies, and a set of tools and demonstrated procedures to apply the platform and the standard proven to guarantee specified productivity, cost, and safety improvements. The envisioned platform will provide a digital representation of the construction product at hand and allow to collect real-time digital data before, during, and after production of the product to continuously monitor changes in the environment and within the production process. Based on the platform, ASHVIN will develop and demonstrate applications that use the digital twin data. These applications will allow it to fully leverage the potential of the IoT based digital twin platform to reach the expected impacts (better scheduling forecast by 20%; better allocation of resources and optimization of equipment usage; reduced number of accidents; reduction of construction projects). The ASHVIN solutions will overcome worker protection and privacy issues that come with the tracking of construction activities, provide means to fuse video data and sensor data, integrate geo-monitoring data, provide multi-physics simulation methods for digital representing the behavior of a product (not only its shape), provide evidence based engineering methods to design for productivity and safety, provide 4D simulation and visualization methods of construction processes, and develop a lean planning process supported by real-time data. All innovations will be demonstrated on real-world construction projects across Europe. The ASHVIN consortium combines strong R&I players from 9 EU member states with strong expertise in construction and engineering management, digital twin technology, IoT, and data security / privacy.

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1 INTRODUCTION

Within WP8 of ASHVIN project the objective is to develop a plan in terms of communication, dissemination & exploitation to position ASHVIN as a European benchmark in the application of Digital Twins to the construction industry.

This deliverable report compiles the exploitable results achieved by the ASHVIN project since its inception. The contributions include all peer-reviewed and technical publications, source code repository, open research data, educational material, and standardization/open-source contributions.

First, the success of projects supported by Horizon 2020 depends not only on novel findings but also on efficient exploitation methods in the dynamic field of research and innovation. Of all these projects, ASHVIN is notable for its audacious goals and progressive methodology. This document functions as a thorough guide, providing details on the target markets, obstacles, competitive environment, business strategy, and strategic framework of ASHVIN. By working together with its partners, ASHVIN has carefully investigated important exploitable outcomes, setting the groundwork for its upcoming initiatives. These pages contain priceless market insights that shed light on the various industries in which ASHVIN's inventions have potential.

Examining this study will take us on a trip to comprehend the complex relationship between strategic exploitation and high-quality research, two factors that are critical to ASHVIN's trajectory toward successful commercialization and significant benefits to society.

In addition, the report presents the innovative Digital Twin Toolkit and explains the ASHVIN Exploitation plan. This cutting-edge toolkit, painstakingly developed through collaborative development by esteemed universities throughout Europe, has the potential to completely transform the construction process. ASHVIN's toolbox is a living example of innovation and advancement, ranging from real-time simulation for construction site planning to generative design capabilities.

The study also provides a thorough examination of ASHVIN's Asset Portfolio, which includes a wide range of instruments intended to improve safety management, construction monitoring, design optimization, performance assessment, and other areas. Every tool is an outcome of industry partners and prestigious universities working together, and it demonstrates ASHVIN's dedication to promoting innovation and real-world effect.

This paper bears witness to ASHVIN's unwavering commitment to excellence, innovation, and revolutionary change in the construction sector as it advances toward commercialization and societal benefits. By means of strategic exploitation and superior research, ASHVIN is able to completely reshape the building industry and establish unprecedented benchmarks for resilience, sustainability, and efficiency.

2 ASHVIN IMPACT FRAMEWORK

D8.1 (Papanikolaou, 2020) of ASHVIN outlines the project impact master plan. The master plan comprises of comprising communication, dissemination and exploitation plans aiming to provide a holistic outreach strategy of the project, leading to success. The plan was developed through an extended fermentation and zymosis process among project partners, each of one representing different stakeholder groups, to reflect their positions and views within this plan for ensuring maximum impact.

In terms of engagement ASHVIN implements an **Agile Stakeholder Engagement Framework** - a methodology designed to continuously develop and strengthen work streams with key stakeholder groups, empowering the operation of the programme as introduced in the Grant Agreement.

Figure 1: : ASHVIN's Stakeholder Engagement Framework (D8.1)

3 ASHVIN EXPLOITATION

The ASHVIN Digital Twin Toolkit, which offers a wide range of state-of-the-art instruments painstakingly designed to modernize every aspect of the construction lifecycle, heralds a revolutionary age in the construction industry. Every tool in the ASHVIN suite was carefully crafted to maximize the potential of Internet of Things-driven digital twin technology through joint development by prestigious institutions and organizations throughout Europe. The ASHVIN toolkit is a prime example of innovation, from the GEN tool's generative design capabilities that allow designers to prioritize safety, resource efficiency, and productivity over a myriad of other options, to the DES tool's real-time simulation for construction site planning that permits stochastic modeling of activities and layouts.

ASHVIN skilfully meets crucial industry needs with products like the 4DV-D and 4DV-C tools, which offer user-friendly visualizations for design impact assessment and construction monitoring, and the SMT tool, which protects worker privacy while improving safety management through simulation and training. In addition, instruments such as the CMT and RISA guarantee smooth configuration management and risk-based status evaluation, enabling well-informed decision-making over project lifespans. The ASHVIN Digital Twin Toolkit is an integrated ecosystem that promotes cooperation, creativity, and ongoing improvement rather than just a set of standalone tools.

Through the smooth integration of digital twin data across several tools and platforms, ASHVIN facilitates comprehensive insights into construction projects for stakeholders, hence promoting informed decision-making across the whole process. Moreover, the modular design of the toolkit facilitates flexibility and scalability, meeting a range of project requirements and changing industry demands. ASHVIN ensures smooth adoption and maximum effect by facilitating seamless interaction with current procedures and technologies, all while adhering to open standards and interoperability. ASHVIN is a shining example of progress, promoting resilience, sustainability, and efficiency in projects of all sizes and complexity as the construction sector embraces digital change.

ASHVIN offers numerous opportunities to turn a profit and position itself as a pioneer in the digital revolution of the construction sector. First off, ASHVIN may provide project developers, engineering firms, and construction corporations with its cutting-edge digital twin toolkit by implementing a license or subscription approach. Because customers pay to access the suite of capabilities, this model guarantees a consistent flow of income. In addition, ASHVIN offers significant expertise and assistance that clients are ready to pay for, such as consultation and implementation services to help clients integrate and optimize the use of the digital twin toolkit inside their current processes.

Additionally, ASHVIN can make money off the data produced by its platform by charging for advanced analytics and insights services that give customers useful data for maximizing efficiency, productivity, and security. Through joint projects and ventures, partnerships with other technology suppliers, building firms, and industry stakeholders can also open new revenue streams. ASHVIN can also provide upgrades, add-ons, and premium features to its toolbox to maximize revenue potential while meeting the varied needs of its clientele. Finally, ASHVIN can charge for access to the marketplace and enable transactions between suppliers and third-party developers by setting up a marketplace for digital twin solutions. In the digital era of the construction industry, ASHVIN is well-positioned to create sustainable growth and profitability through these methods and a dedication to innovation.

4 ASHVIN ASSET PORTFOLIO

4.1 BRICS¹

Performance Indicator (PI) assessment of solutions in the design space

The BRICS tool uses imbedded mathematical algorithms to calculate PI values, which aids in decision-making. To guarantee performance-based design, the design solutions are ranked and scored using the computed PI values. The BRICS computation results can be included back into the EBD tool to enhance the knowledge base and facilitate the iterative design process of the GEN Tool.

Sofistik2CarbonFootprint

Information | Table | By Group | History | Comparison

project_ID:	Deck Area:		
2965	1110 [m ²]		
carbon footprint:	footprint per area:	Rating:	
2155.2 [t CO ₂ e]	1.9 [t CO ₂ e/m ²]	3.4	

Upload CDB

Browse... 2965.cdb
Upload complete

Projektnummer
2965

Datum
2021-12-09

Save to Database
 Save to History

Start

Download Report

¹ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=018-f6MRo-w>

Information	Table	By Group	History	Comparison
title	volume	weight	footprint	length
Anschluss Haenger Bogen	0.68	5.87	14.68	11.24
Beton Bogen	NA	50.00	8.00	NA
Beton Deck	NA	315.00	50.40	NA
Boegen	6.38	55.07	137.66	107.57
Deck	51.15	421.61	1054.03	335.60
Haenger	0.12	1.04	2.61	284.32
Querprofile	3.16	27.29	68.21	52.38
Quertraeger	5.86	28.59	71.48	177.31
Stahl sonstige	NA	110.00	275.00	NA
Stahl zusaetzlich	NA	110.00	275.00	NA
Stuetzen	8.68	74.93	187.33	160.54
Zugband	0.48	4.14	10.75	98.66

Sofistik2CarbonFootprint

Upload CDB

Browse... 2965.cdb

Projektnummer

Datum

Save to Database
 Save to History

4.1.1 TOOL OWNER

schlaich bergemann partner

schlaich bergemann Partner is headquartered in Stuttgart, Germany, and has additional offices in Berlin, New York, São Paulo, Shanghai, Paris, Madrid, and Los Angeles. The

firm specializes primarily in lightweight structures for bridge design, membrane and cable structures, glass architecture, and associated fields.

4.1.2 TOOL EXPLOITATION – COMMERCIAL AND RESEARCH

The BRICS (Bridge AnalytlCS) tool is a valuable resource for construction industry stakeholders, particularly around footbridge design. First, by automating Performance Indicator (PI) computations, it simplifies design processes and frees up designers to concentrate on creative elements. Second, BRICS gives decision-makers critical metrics—such as resource efficiency, structural integrity, and safety—so they may make well-informed decisions. Thirdly, it reduces costs and improves project outcomes by detecting inefficiencies and optimizing resource allocation. Furthermore, by proactively evaluating safety risks early in the design phase, BRICS helps to mitigate risk. Furthermore, it promotes continuous improvement by continuously gathering and analysing data to enhance algorithms and guaranteeing that best practices are updated. Lastly, BRICS makes it easier to streamline documentation and reporting, which promotes efficient decision-making and communication across project teams. To sum up, BRICS is an essential instrument for promoting safety, efficiency, and creativity in footbridge design, which is advantageous for business ventures as well as research projects in the construction industry.

4.2 EBD²

Evidence Based design (EBD) support tool for recycling historic data as input at the early project stages

Using compiled historical data (from previous project designs and the completed physical infrastructure) from an existing knowledge base, the EBD tool assists the AEC early project stage by offering design predictions, warnings, and recommendations.

These three elements guarantee the production of superior designs. The parametric model for the GEN Tool is created using the EBD tool's outputs.

Data from the built environment and future designs can be added to the EBD tool to further enhance it.

Parameter Input

bridge length:

20 m 30 m 200 m

20 38 56 74 92 110 128 146 164 182 200

bridge width:

2 m 4 m 10 m

2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

Prefabrication

prefabricaton space available

ability to deliver big parts

bridge typology

no selection

² <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=VCSnSCqni7Y&t=40s>

Predictions, Recommendations and Warnings based on the 5 most similar bridge projects from a total of 46 projects.

Construction Cost

Construction Time

Carbon Footprint

Dimension Recommendations

Warnings

A bridge of type girder would benefit from prefabrication, which is not possible on site. Maybe consider a different Bridge typology.

No accidents were recorded in the similar projects.

Selected similar projects

1. nearest	2. nearest	3. nearest	4. nearest	5. nearest
<p>2945 Cost: 3,259 € Construction Time: 4 Days Embodied Carbon: 1,286 kg Co2</p> <p>Safety incidents: None</p>	<p>3308 Cost: 3,927 € Construction Time: 2 Days Embodied Carbon: 886 kg Co2</p> <p>Safety incidents: None</p>	<p>3560 Cost: NA € Construction Time: 3 Days Embodied Carbon: NA kg Co2</p> <p>Safety incidents: None</p>	<p>2215 Cost: 2,368 € Construction Time: NA Days Embodied Carbon: 190 kg Co2</p> <p>Safety incidents: None</p>	<p>3222 Cost: 8,163 € Construction Time: 2 Days Embodied Carbon: NA kg Co2</p> <p>Safety incidents: None</p>

4.2.1 TOOL OWNER

Technical University of Berlin

Technische Universität Berlin, located solely in Berlin, Germany, provides a collaborative environment for students and faculty. Alongside its main campus, it offers dedicated workspaces designed to foster innovation and research. Known for its emphasis on engineering and technology, TU Berlin supports interdisciplinary studies, particularly in fields such as lightweight structures, membrane and cable systems, glass architecture, and related areas.

4.2.2 TOOL EXPLOITATION – COMMERCIAL AND RESEARCH

For engineers, designers, and decision-makers alike, the EBD (Evidence-Based Design) Assistant provides invaluable commercial applications in the early phases of footbridge projects. The utilisation of historical data allows for the provision of informative key performance indicators, such as construction time and cost, which facilitate well-informed decision-making with respect to project requirements and site selection. Unlike other options, its methodical methodology closes a market gap by providing customized design exploration for footbridge projects. Stakeholders may efficiently navigate the design space with the help of predictions, alerts, and recommendations presented in an easy-

to-use interface. The tool's commercial worth is further reinforced by its capacity to provide insights into sensor placement throughout building or maintenance stages, which optimizes resource allocation and improves safety measures. By offering possibilities for enhancing databases of footbridge designs and investigating potential prototype implementations, the EBD Tool in research advances the field of evidence-based design in infrastructure development

4.3 GEN³

Generative design modeller to support design for productivity, resource efficiency and safety

Building generative design techniques that let designers automatically come up with a ton of options given a set of input parameters. Users will be able to rate each option using the program according to established KPIs for resource efficiency, productivity, and safety.

³ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=hF1efZ631eQ&t=28s>

4.3.1 TOOL OWNER

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Technische Universität Berlin, located solely in Berlin, Germany, provides a collaborative environment for students and faculty. Alongside its main campus, it offers dedicated workspaces designed to foster innovation and research. Known for its emphasis on engineering and technology, TU Berlin supports interdisciplinary studies, particularly in fields such as lightweight structures, membrane and cable systems, glass architecture, and related areas.

4.3.2 TOOL EXPLOITATION – COMMERCIAL AND RESEARCH

Bridge design and construction techniques are being revolutionized using the GEN (Generative Design) tool, which is being used in both commercial and research contexts. Commercially, it establishes geometric extents and limitations for important characteristics like length, width, and thickness by utilizing historical data from the EBD (Experience-Based Design) tool, enabling effective parametric modelling. By utilizing sophisticated optimization methods like non-dominated genetic algorithms, GEN makes it easier to investigate different design options to optimize performance metrics while respecting design limitations. Using rigorous analysis in programs such as Microsoft Excel and visualization on the ASHVIN DT platform, it helps choose the best bridge designs for additional development. Furthermore, by calculating performance metrics from digital twin data, the integration with the BRICS tool

guarantees continual improvement and enhances the knowledge library kept on the ASHVIN platform. By giving researchers the resources, they need to investigate novel approaches, carry out optimization studies, examine data-driven insights from previous projects, and eventually enhance our understanding of bridge design and construction techniques, GEN promotes innovation in the field of study.

4.4 DES⁴

Simulation-based real-time construction site and logistics planning tool

A tool for configuring discrete event stochastic simulations of site layouts and scheduled construction operations. Stochastic productivity data recorded by the ASHVIN digital twin platform will be utilized by the instrument.

⁴ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=yFA79ePpfW8>

PROJECTS Demo 5 Kineum office building (DES Tool) User

- Doors
- Dry wall first side
- Dry wall second side
- Ventilation
- Plumbing
- Electricity
- Floor
- Paint
- Dry ceiling

TIME OPTION 1 NONE x1 AUTOSCROLL

TASKS 0.065

- Dry wall first side WS1
- Dry wall first side WS2
- Ventilation WS1
- Dry wall first side WS3
- Plumbing WS1
- Ventilation WS2

PROJECTS Demo 5 Kineum office building (DES Tool) User

- Doors
- Dry wall first side
- Dry wall second side
- Ventilation
- Plumbing
- Electricity
- Floor
- Paint
- Dry ceiling

TIME OPTION 1 NONE x1 AUTOSCROLL

TASKS 0.253

- Plumbing WS2
- Electricity WS1
- Ventilation WS3
- Plumbing WS3
- Electricity WS2
- Dry wall second side WS1

PROJECTS Demo 5 Kineum office building (DES Tool) User

As-designed

As-built (DEMO)

TIME OPTION 2 OPTION 4

0.038

TASKS

- Electricity WS3
- Ventilation WS3
- Plumbing WS3
- Electricity WS2
- Dry wall second side WS1
- Electricity WS3

PROJECTS Demo 5 Kineum office building (DES Tool) User

MEDIAN_DURATION_DAYS

Option	Median Duration (days)
Option 0	155
Option 1	87.0
Option 2	58.0

RE_CARPENTER

Option	RE CARPENTER (%)
Option 0	1.0
Option 1	0.59
Option 2	0.90

RE_DRY_CONSTRUCTOR

Option	RE DRY CONSTRUCTOR (%)
Option 0	0.67
Option 1	1.0
Option 2	0.86

RE_ELECTRICIAN

Option	RE ELECTRICIAN (%)
Option 0	1.0
Option 1	0.32
Option 2	1.0

Duration (days)

Option 0 (blue), Option 1 (orange), Option 2 (green)

	Option 1	Option 2	Option 3
Workspaces	1	3	3
Number dry constructor	4	4	10
Number HVAC	4	4	9
Number plumbing	2	2	1
Number electrician	2	2	1
Number painter	4	4	2
Number floor layer	4	4	5
Number carpenter	2	2	4

4.4.1 TOOL OWNER

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Technische Universität Berlin, located solely in Berlin, Germany, provides a collaborative environment for students and faculty. Alongside its main campus, it offers dedicated workspaces designed to foster innovation and research. Known for its emphasis on engineering and technology, TU Berlin supports interdisciplinary studies, particularly in fields such as lightweight structures, membrane and cable systems, glass architecture, and related areas.

4.4.2 TOOL EXPLOITATION – COMMERCIAL AND RESEARCH

A new paradigm in construction management is introduced by the DES (Discrete Event Simulation) tool, which makes it possible to simulate site activities in real time and assess key performance indicators (KPIs). It provides unmatched insights into safety, productivity, and resource efficiency—all of which are essential for making well-informed decisions during the design and implementation of projects. In contrast to previous approaches, DES effectively addresses dynamic construction issues by utilizing stochastic modelling and real-time data. Its economic potential is in process optimization via real-time insights and simulations-based site layout modifications, resource allocation, and supply chain adjustments. DES is still developing because of continuous study, offering further opportunities for cost savings, risk reduction, and project planning

improvements. A new age of efficiency, accuracy, and stakeholder satisfaction is brought in by its integration into the construction sector.

4.5 4DV-D

Construction site simulator for early design phases with 4D visualizer

With the help of this program, it will be possible to see exactly how different design choices will affect output, resource efficiency, and safety. It is possible to compare several possibilities with one another by putting anticipated construction sequences on display.

4.5.1 TOOL OWNER

Digital Twin Technology

Digital Twin Technology is a technology company that is creating digital twin for various industries like construction, smart cities. They are optimizing ideation process and planning with the support of a digital twin. Design construction sites or the entire city digitally and simulate their characteristics virtually. Plan, simulate and engineer the site digitally. Evaluate and assess the performance of real infrastructure like building, bridges, tunnels etc. in real-time and order to optimize all continuously.

4.5.2 TOOL EXPLOITATION – COMMERCIAL AND RESEARCH

For construction project planners, the 4DV-D (4D Construction Site Simulator for Design Phase) tool is an essential tool. Based on important performance metrics like safety and cost, it facilitates well-informed decision-making by visualizing building sequences and design options. From a business perspective, it helps choose the best design while adhering to project specifications and limitations. It also promotes integrated project delivery by making forecasts based on performance indicators. Its research promise also resides in developing 4D planning systems that include complicated construction activity simulation and multi-viewport comparison. For comprehensive project management, studies can also examine integration with logistical planning, spatial planning, and health and safety management. In the end, the 4DV-D tool is a fundamental component of digital construction and collaborative planning, helping all parties involved to understand designs and make informed decisions.

4.6 4DV-C⁵

Construction monitoring tool with productivity and safety KPI decision making dashboard

A four-dimensional tool that tracks activities using the digital twin platform to visualize previous construction efforts. Using precisely recorded historical activity, the program makes it possible to forecast future construction sequences and site layout possibilities.

⁵ https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=PY38H2_b5aw&t=124s

4.6.1 TOOL OWNER

Digital Twin Technology

DigitalTwin Technology is a technology company that is creating digital twin for various industries like construction, smart cities. They are optimizing ideation process and planning with the support of a digital twin. Design construction sites or the entire city digitally and simulate their characteristics virtually. Plan, simulate and engineer the site digitally. Evaluate and assess the performance of real infrastructure like building, bridges, tunnels etc. in real-time and order to optimize all continuously.

4.6.2 TOOL EXPLOITATION – COMMERCIAL AND RESEARCH

The 4DV-C tool is supposed to be used by construction companies and in particular the planning department and construction managers. And 4D construction digital twins take that 4D model and integrating information from construction site sensors that allows you to understand the model and its performance. The construction digital twin in 4DV-C provides a simulative environment, allowing teams to digitally test construction sequencing and logistics scenarios, verify the as-built situation, or run what-if simulations using live data from building sensors to optimize performance and sustainability. In terms of outcomes the use of 4DV-C facilitates improved outcomes through construction-model focused progress tracking, production planning and analyse & simulate different construction workflows to optimize project execution as optimized scheduling can reduce labor cost and improve labor productivity.

4.7 SMT⁶

Privacy ensuring safety management, simulation, and training tool.

An app that will let safety managers examine historical construction activity and identify potential safety risks on the job site without having the ability to manually target individual workers.

⁶ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=yFA79ePpfW8>

4.7.1 TOOL OWNER

Digital Twin Technology

Digital Twin Technology is a technology company that is creating digital twin for various industries like construction, smart cities. They are optimizing ideation process and

planning with the support of a digital twin. Design construction sites or the entire city digitally and simulate their characteristics virtually. Plan, simulate and engineer the site digitally. Evaluate and assess the performance of real infrastructure like building, bridges, tunnels etc. in real-time and order to optimize all continuously.

4.7.2 TOOL EXPLOITATION – COMMERCIAL AND RESEARCH

The SMT tool aims to improve safety on construction site in terms of theft & burglary alongside safe working conditions for construction workers. Since construction site is subjected to crimes frequently the tool target construction companies & sub-contractors, site owners and site managers on the actual site to reduce such crimes This tool can detect unwanted presence in a space, which may prevent or notify the site management of possible criminal activities, without violating privacy issues. Another potential use case regards health and safety. Presence outside approved work hours can indicate injured personnel and the site manager can then quickly act.

The SMT tool also incorporates functionalities aimed at reducing injury rate on construction site. This is facilitated through establishing a connected construction site where various devices and systems are interconnected and can interact. This integrated technology can identify potential hazards and triggering alerts, thereby playing a crucial role in incident minimization and prevention. The tool can also act as an inspiration for software developers who are planning to provide secure IoT data collection and data fusion methods from multiple sources and develop digital twin solutions for construction sites

4.8 CMT⁷

A configuration management tool to track as-designed and as-built, as well as, to allow for seamless commissioning

Software based on digital twin data that will enable the establishment and maintenance of consistency throughout the project lifecycle between requirements, design, configuration items, and related construction, operations, and maintenance data, equipment, and other enablers.

⁷ https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=PY38H2_b5aw&t=124s

4.8.1 TOOL OWNER

Digital Twin Technology

Digital Twin Technology is a technology company that is creating digital twin for various industries like construction, smart cities. They are optimizing ideation process and planning with the support of a digital twin. Design construction sites or the entire city digitally and simulate their characteristics virtually. Plan, simulate and engineer the site digitally. Evaluate and assess the performance of real infrastructure like building, bridges, tunnels etc. in real-time and order to optimize all continuously.

4.8.2 TOOL EXPLOITATION – COMMERCIAL AND RESEARCH

The (CMT) ensures quality throughout the project lifetime by facilitating real-time monitoring and assessment with digital twin technologies. It optimizes resource allocation and minimizes rework by streamlining configuration management procedures. The (CMT) automates quality checks and ensures compliance with standards and regulations by incorporating IoT data. It provides a forum for research and development aimed at tackling changing industry problems. In terms of business, the (CMT) offers a competitive edge, drawing in customers looking for creative solutions and accelerating the digital transformation of the construction industry. In summary, the (CMT) improves quality, efficiency, and competitiveness in the industry and is a useful tool for businesses.

4.9 RISA

Risk-based status assessment tool with KPI dashboard

A visual aid that makes it possible to comprehend an asset's condition in detail and create maintenance schedules that are optimally designed.

4.9.1 TOOL OWNER

Infra plan Konzalting.

Infra Plan Consulting specializes in data analytics, maintenance planning, and infrastructure management, offering decision support tools that integrate advanced technologies for data collection and utilization. With a focus on upgrading transport networks, their expert team engages in R&D activities spanning condition assessment, construction, and maintenance management.

4.9.2 TOOL EXPLOITATION – COMMERCIAL AND RESEARCH

The RISA (Risk-Based Asset Management Tool) incorporates risk assessment into decision-making procedures, thereby revolutionizing asset management. Infrastructure managers can use it to examine several maintenance scenarios according to user preferences, asset condition, and financial limitations. Through resource allocation optimization and maintenance activity prioritization, the RISA technology maximizes asset resilience and performance while lowering risks. Through the facilitation of proactive maintenance planning and cost-effective risk management measures, it provides asset owners and managers with a commercial edge. Additionally, the RISA tool promotes innovation and advances in infrastructure maintenance by driving research and development in asset management techniques.

4.10 MatchFEM⁸

Multi-physics model matching tool for status assessment of bridges and buildings

Techniques that were put into practice to enable the stochastically changing of input parameters utilizing sensor-based observations for various Multiphysics simulations. Accurate representation of behavioural digital twins will be possible with these techniques.

⁸ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=4A-ar2dBFoE>

4.10.1 TOOL OWNER

The Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya · BarcelonaTech (UPC) is a renowned public institution dedicated to higher education and research, specializing in engineering, architecture, science, and technology. Its state-of-the-art scientific and technological infrastructure serves as a hub for research groups, students, professionals, and industry partners, fostering collaboration and driving societal and economic impact.

4.10.2 TOOL EXPLOITATION – COMMERCIAL AND RESEARCH

In the built environment, MatchFEM offers a revolutionary method for combining digital twins (DT), measurements, and simulations. MatchFEM empowers informed decision-making throughout the asset lifecycle by enabling the smooth merging of different data sources. In the commercial sector, MatchFEM provides a complete solution to optimize maintenance strategies, boost resource efficiency, and increase asset performance for engineers, designers, supervisors, and asset owners. By utilizing its features, companies may create predictive maintenance plans, evaluate simulations using real-world data, and simulate different scenarios to reduce risk. Furthermore, MatchFEM advances the integration of external simulation engines, simulated data, and multi-physics models within DT platforms, promoting innovation in asset management techniques and furthering research. MatchFEM's event-driven architecture and modular design provide scalability, flexibility, and adaptation to meet changing industry demands.

4.11 GIS

GIS integrator for digital twin-based Asset management

An asset management KPI-specific set of digital twin expected statuses for various assets can be monitored by asset managers using a GIS tool.

4.11.1 TOOL OWNER

Infra plan Konzalting.

Infra Plan Consulting specializes in data analytics, maintenance planning, and infrastructure management, offering decision support tools that integrate advanced technologies for data collection and utilization. With a focus on upgrading transport networks, their expert team engages in R&D activities spanning condition assessment, construction, and maintenance management.

4.11.2 TOOL EXPLOITATION – COMMERCIAL AND RESEARCH

By combining condition assessment, maintenance, and monitoring into a single, comprehensive GIS-based system, the GISI (GIS Integrator Tool) completely transforms asset management. Asset managers can use it to visualize infrastructure assets, evaluate their state, and determine maintenance priorities according to risk levels. The GISI tool uses AI-powered fault detection models and UAV technology to automate the inspection process, increasing productivity and accuracy. It improves performance and safety across a range of infrastructure types, such as highways, bridges, and airports. In the commercial world, the GISI tool gives asset managers and owners a competitive edge, drawing in customers looking for cutting-edge asset management solutions. Additionally, it creates opportunities for research and development in the areas of performance prediction and infrastructure maintenance, boosting industrial innovation.

5 CONCLUSION AND FUTURE RESEARCH

In conclusion, the ASHVIN project is a shining example of innovation in the construction sector, with the potential to completely change the industry thanks to its ground breaking work with digital twins. ASHVIN has established a strong framework for optimizing its impact and achievement, which guides its communication, distribution, and exploitation efforts using a rigorous Impact Framework.

Utilizing the Digital Twin Toolkit from ASHVIN offers previously unheard-of possibilities to transform the building lifecycle, from safety monitoring to design optimization. As a result of its creative business models, open standards, and strategic alliances, ASHVIN is well-positioned to take advantage of these opportunities and promote long-term, profitable growth.

FUTURE RESEARCH:

Future research projects will build on and investigate the ground-breaking work that has already been completed as ASHVIN develops. Important topics needing additional study include:

Advanced Tool Development: Improving and refining already-existing tools in the ASHVIN Digital Twin Toolkit to better handle new possibilities and challenges in the construction sector.

Including Emerging Technologies: investigation of cutting-edge technologies like blockchain, machine learning, and artificial intelligence to enhance the potential of digital twins and open new creative directions.

Enhanced Data Analytics: Utilizing cutting-edge analytics methods to extract valuable information from the massive volumes of data produced by digital twins, allowing for better decision-making and process optimization in the building industry.

Collaboration and Stakeholder Engagement: To make sure that ASHVIN's innovations are in line with practical demands and specifications, there should be ongoing communication with important stakeholders, such as industry partners, legislators, and end users.

Sustainability and Resilience: An investigation into the ways in which Digital Twins can be applied to improve sustainability and resilience in the construction sector, with a focus on reducing environmental impact, optimizing resource usage, and reducing risks related to natural disasters and climate change.

By following these research directions, ASHVIN will keep pushing the envelope of innovation and solidifying its position as a pioneer in the construction industry's use of digital twins, resulting in real benefits for society and influencing the direction of building in Europe and beyond.

LIMITATIONS

Technological Complexity: Using Digital Twins in the construction industry requires integrating several cutting-edge technologies, including data analytics, IoT sensors, and simulation tools. Overcoming the intricacy of these systems and guaranteeing smooth interoperability might present formidable obstacles.

Data Integrity and Quality: Sensors, BIM models, and historical data are just a few of the types of data that digital twins primarily rely on. It might be difficult to guarantee the reliability,

consistency, and quality of these data sources, especially when working with outdated software and different data formats.

Cost and Resource Limitations: Creating and implementing Digital Twins in building projects calls for large expenditures on IT infrastructure, qualified labour, and continuing upkeep. The broad adoption of digital twins may be hampered by financial and resource constraints, especially for smaller businesses and projects with tighter budgets.

Security and Privacy Issues: Privacy, security, and data ownership are among the issues brought up by the gathering and exchange of sensitive data inside digital twins. To reduce the dangers connected with data breaches and illegal access, it is crucial to guarantee strong data protection procedures and regulatory compliance.

Cultural and Industry Resistance: Historically, the building sector has been hesitant to embrace new methods and technologies. Key hurdles for the widespread adoption of Digital Twins include overcoming opposition to change, addressing cultural barriers, and encouraging a culture of creativity and collaboration among stakeholders.

Interoperability and Standards: To fully realize the potential impact of Digital Twins, smooth interoperability across many platforms and systems is essential. To facilitate cooperation and compatibility amongst various projects and stakeholders, it is imperative to establish common standards and protocols for data sharing, interoperability, and integration.

Scalability and Generalizability: Although digital twins have a lot to offer construction projects, more research must be done on how well they scale and generalize to other project types, scales, and contexts. Tailoring Digital Twins to the distinct needs and limitations of various construction projects could necessitate specialized solutions and iterative improvement.

The ASHVIN project can enhance its influence and facilitate the wider integration and execution of Digital Twins in the construction sector by tackling these constraints and obstacles.

REFERENCES

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